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Industrial Work Heritage in the Manzanese: Memory, Archives, and Audiovisual Storytelling

Post-Conference Research Report

Conference “Valorizzare il territorio con la Cultura della Sedia”, Manzano, September 6th, 2025, at Cluster Cluster Legno Arredo Casa FVG

The research project *Industrial Work Heritage in the Manzanese: Memory, Archives, and Audiovisual Storytelling* is situated within a broader regional effort to document, preserve, and reinterpret the historical, social, and material heritage generated by the “Distretto della Sedia”, the historical industrial cluster of chair production located in the Province of Udine, known for its dense network of small and medium enterprises specializing in wood processing and furniture manufacturing. The project was initiated in early 2025 in collaboration with the Municipality of Manzano as part of a shared commitment to examining the forms of memory embedded in local industrial culture. The conference “*Valorizzare il territorio con la Cultura della Sedia*”, held on 6 September 2025 in Manzano, provided a significant opportunity to present the first outcomes of this research to a diverse audience, including municipal authorities, local enterprises, archival specialists, and representatives from cultural and design institutions.

The central ambition of the research is to understand how the memory of industrial labour in the Manzanese has been constructed, preserved, and transmitted, and how it might be reinterpreted today through audiovisual and narrative approaches. The study investigates the coexistence of multiple forms of memory—individual, collective, institutional, and corporate—and examines how these forms intersect, diverge, or conflict. The project is grounded in a critical understanding of memory as a dynamic process consisting of acquisition, preservation, and reuse. Rather than being a static record of the past, memory constantly reconfigures itself each time it is activated; it is shaped by present needs and interpretative frameworks. This premise guides the analysis of industrial archives not merely as repositories of historical documents but as active instruments that can support the production of new narratives.

The research adopts a multidisciplinary approach, integrating archival studies, ethnographic methods, contemporary visual analysis, and participatory practices. Three dimensions structure the methodology. The first is inquiry and ethnography, through which the researcher seeks to understand the socio-historical context of industrial labour in the Manzanese, including its spatial organization, its gendered division of labour, and its connection to the private sphere. The second dimension consists of artistic and visual practices grounded in archival materials, which enable the examination and reinterpretation of documents beyond their original function. The third component involves participatory and digital ethnography, aiming to encourage the contribution of the local community and to collect dispersed materials, oral histories, and personal archives that complement or challenge institutional holdings.

Labour

The starting point for the research lies in earlier studies on the industrial history of the district. While numerous publications document the evolution of chair manufacturing and the achievements of local design, the processes, labour conditions, and material practices that constitute the foundation of this production have received comparatively limited attention. The distinction between corporate storytelling and community narratives is central to this gap. Corporate storytelling tends to focus on the excellence of the final product—chairs—while relegating labour to the background. Community narratives, by contrast, highlight the lived experience of work, the permeability between domestic and industrial spaces, and the social networks that sustain production. The project investigates the relationship between these two forms of narration, analyzing whether they should be considered complementary or whether their divergence reveals deeper structural imbalances.

A major reference for the research is the volume *Qualità del lavoro e qualità della vita*, published by the Municipality of Manzano in 2002. This publication offered an early and significant attempt to connect labour to everyday life and included an extensive gender survey on women working in the district. The study provided essential insights into the social and economic roles of women and served as an initial conceptual anchor for the current research. Another foundational reference is the RAI documentary *Ragazze di un paese con fabbriche* (1980), directed by Elio Bartolini. The film follows four women workers across a full day, offering an intimate portrayal of their working rhythms, aspirations, and challenges. Together, these works foregrounded the centrality of women's labour within the district and underscored the importance of a gendered perspective in the analysis of industrial memory.

(Re)discovering women's representation in local archives

Building upon this foundation, the research examined two archival collections held by the Municipality of Manzano. The first is the Gazzino Archive, consisting of ninety-five photographs produced by Urbano Gazzino, a worker from Montbel who documented factory life between the 1960s and 1980s. The images testify to everyday industrial practices, including assembly, finishing, preparation of components, and collaborative work. The archive frequently includes images of women workers, portrayed both individually and collectively, engaged in manual and technical tasks. The presence of handwritten notes on the reverse side of many prints provides additional contextual information, linking personal identity, workplace activities, and memory. The archive offers a unique view from within the factory, reflecting both the technical dimension of production and the social relationships that shaped the labour environment.

The second collection, the Promosedia Archive, covers more than thirty years of promotional materials, spanning from the late 1970s to the early 2010s, including design competitions, exhibitions, and marketing documents produced by the institutional organization representing the chair district. In contrast to the Gazzino Archive, this collection constructs a narrative centred on the product rather than the labour. Chairs appear as autonomous objects, often isolated from their context of production. Workers, particularly women, are largely absent. Even in competitions such as *Una sedia italiana per gli USA* (1984), where the designer Michela Baldessari was among the winners, female authorship remains rare within the

broader corpus. This scarcity reveals a structural imbalance in the visual representation of the district, in which the visibility of designed objects contrasts sharply with the invisibility of the labour force that created them.

Figures 1 and 2. Photographs from the Gazzino Archive (left) and the Promosedia Archive (right)

The juxtaposition of these two archives exposes the non-neutrality of archival representation. Industrial archives do not passively document reality; they reflect specific institutional priorities and reinforce certain narratives while omitting others. The lack of visibility of female labour in Promosedia materials contrasts with its strong presence in internal photographic records such as those by Gazzino. This discrepancy motivated the development of an initial thematic inventory focusing on gender representation, aiming to classify and contextualize visual evidence of women's participation in the district. The inventory is intended as a preliminary tool for guiding future research and for supporting more inclusive archival and heritage practices.

New storytelling models proposals

The research also includes the development of contemporary creative outputs informed by archival sources, aimed at exploring new models of industrial heritage storytelling. A notable example is *Diversamente Blu*, a series of visual interventions created through graphic annotations and chromatic overlays on historical photographs. The project emphasizes the presence of women workers by rendering female figures in blue—a chromatic choice inspired both by discussions with local industry professionals on gendered corporate symbolism, including references to the so-called “Confindustria pink quota,” and by the broader issue of women's recurrent invisibility in the district's visual history. Conceived as a dual-screen installation, the work juxtaposes two complementary narrative registers: on one side, archival images depicting women in factory settings, enriched with blue-based graphic interventions as a metaphor for the visibility and invisibility of female labour; on the other, textual contributions from younger generations, featuring reflections and phrases collected from female students in local scientific and technical high schools, which serve as an intergenerational counter-narrative. Although conceptual in nature, these visual studies are designed to support future dissemination initiatives and public engagement activities, offering alternative interpretive tools for understanding industrial heritage through a gender-sensitive lens.

Figures 3. *Diversamente Blu*, Fabien Marques, dual screen installation, 2025

The project also explores integrating other visual forms into heritage storytelling. A prototype of a photographic book (dummy photobook) has been shown, combining archival materials with contemporary documentary imagery, such as detailed close-up shots of the seat upholsterer's hands at work in the "Linea Fabbrica" company (Manzano), in a sequential narrative that connects past and present. The photobook includes visual references that extend beyond the industrial sphere—such as canonical paintings or historical iconography—to stimulate reflection on representation, gender, and labour across time. Alongside this, a creative documentary podcast has been prototyped using artificial intelligence to generate simulated voices. By combining archival research with fictionalized narration—for example, recasting the story of French cinema icon Alain Delon's connection to the local company Sabot—the podcast illustrates how industrial heritage can be reinterpreted through hybrid narrative forms.

Figures 4. *Diversamente Blu* (a dummy book project): *Anna*, Fabien Marques, digital photograph, 2025

Figures 5. *Diversamente Blu* (a dummy book project): *The World's Largest Chair*, Fabien Marques, digital photography collage, 2025

Figures 6. *Diversamente Blu* (a dummy book project): *The letters*, Fabien Marques, digital photography collage, archival documents, 2025

Local community and access to heritage

Engagement with the local community plays a critical role in the research. A public collection station was activated during the conference, inviting residents, former workers, and families to contribute photographs, documents, or oral testimonies. This initiative demonstrated the

existence of a dispersed set of materials and personal narratives that remain outside institutional archives yet are crucial to understanding industrial memory. The contributions collected illustrate the potential for participatory approaches to enrich archival holdings, stimulate intergenerational dialogue, and foster shared responsibility for heritage preservation.

The study also examines digital infrastructures that can facilitate access to heritage. As an example, existing interactive heritage maps—such as those documenting Jewish history in the northeastern United States—illustrate how archival materials can be geolocated, contextualized, and made accessible through intuitive digital platforms. Such models provide inspiration for future digital initiatives in the Manzanese, where geographical distribution of workplaces, factories, and domestic production sites forms an essential component of the district's identity.

The research concludes that the valorization of industrial heritage requires a shift from mere conservation to active reuse. Archives should serve not only as protected repositories but as resources that enable reinterpretation, dialogue, and innovation. Cross-sector collaboration—between municipalities, researchers, artists, enterprises, and educational institutions—is essential to achieve this aim. Initiatives such as artistic residencies, workshops, and educational programmes are especially important to engage younger generations, whose perspectives and participation will shape the future of the district's cultural identity.

Overall, the research demonstrates that industrial memory in the Manzanese is constituted through a multiplicity of narratives—corporate, communal, institutional, and personal. By examining archival representations, highlighting omissions, and proposing new forms of storytelling, the project offers an integrated framework for understanding and reimagining the heritage of labour. Through a combination of critical analysis, archival investigation, participatory engagement, and creative experimentation, it contributes to building a more inclusive, accessible, and dynamic approach to the cultural heritage of the Distretto della Sedia.

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